

OVERVIEW OF EXISTING CAPABILITIES IN EMERGING INSTITUTES

Task 1.2, A1.2.1, A1.2.2

Lenka Kňazovická, Vladimír Urban (CMI)

1 Introduction

Mapping of the current capabilities of JV, CMI, SMU, UL, RISE, DFM and DTU, including equipment inventories, was one of the important tools in the coordination of work within WP1 of the 22RPT03-MultifixRad project. The mapping serves two important purposes: firstly, to establish the baseline status at the institutes at the project start, and secondly to serve as the basis for suggestions of smart specialisation.

The survey was distributed among the participants, and answers were collected via Google Form platform, which allow convenient analysis of the results. All emerging institutes responded to the survey, as well as TÜBITAK. The list of respondents is provided below.

Name	Institute	Country
maniur@smu.gov.sk	SMU	Slovakia
aao@justervesenet.no	JV	Norway
patrik.broberg@rise.se	RISE	Sweden
humbet.nasibli@tubitak.gov.tr	TUBITAK	Turkey
jovan.bojkovski@fe.uni-lj.si	UL	Slovenia
lknazovicka@cmi.cz	CMI	Czech Republic
sqcl@kt.dtu.dk	DTU	Denmark
anr@dfm.dk	DFM	Denmark

It is likely that some of the questions pertaining to current fixed points and the realisation of the ITS-90 have been interpreted differently by different respondents. Some confusion may have arisen as to whether the questions were referring to cells designed for radiometric measurements or whether they were referring to fixed points in general.

2 Survey structure

The survey had two main sections, one devoted to current capabilities at the start of the project, and the other to the aims of each participant. The visual form of the survey can be seen in Fig. 1. The questions asked were as follows:

Current capabilities – scale realisation:

Are you realising ITS-90 temperature scale?

- If yes, in which temperature range?
- Which fixed point(s) do you use?
- Do you have some other fixed points, e.g. for lower temperatures?

Are you realising MeP-K?

- If yes, in which temperature range?
- Which fixed point(s) do you use?
- Which method do you use (absolute, relative)?

Current capabilities - equipment:

Do you have availability to characterise your interpolation device?

- Relative spectral characterisation: Yes, directly in lab/Yes, via another department in our institute/No
- SSE: Yes, directly in lab/Yes, via another department in our institute/No
- Linearity: Yes, directly in lab/Yes, via another department in our institute/No

MultiFixRad

Overview of existing capabilities in less experienced institutes, Task 1.2, A1.2.1, A1.2.2

Do you have available facility for filling HTFPs cell?

- If yes, in which temperature range?

Do you have available machining services?

- If yes, which?

Do you have capabilities for thermal modelling?

- If yes, which SW do you use and which kind of the modelling do you realise?

Do you have capabilities for optics modelling?

- If yes, which SW do you use and which kind of the modelling do you realise?

Do you have capabilities for radiometric modelling, e.g. emissivity?

- If yes, which SW do you use and which kind of the modelling do you realise?

Future capabilities:

Do you plan to extend realisation of ITS-90 temperature scale?

- If yes, in which temperature range?
- Which fixed point(s) do you use?

Do you plan to realise MeP-K?

- If yes, in which temperature range?
- Which fixed point(s) do you plan to use?
- Which method do you plan to implement (absolute, relative)?

Any other Information to share with the partners?

Otázky Odpovede 7 Nastavenia

Sekcia 1 z 3

Current Capabilities - temperature scale realisation

MultiFixRad capabilities survey

E-mail *

Platná e-mailová adresa

Tento formulár zhromažďuje e-mailové adresy. [Zmeniť nastavenia](#)

Do you currently realise ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C? *

Yes

No

If yes, in which temperature range?

Text krátkej odpovede

Which fixed point(s) do you use?

Ag

Figure 1: Overview on the beginning of the survey realised via Google Forms

3 Survey results

First part of the survey was focused on the overview of the current capabilities of participating institutes in realisation of the scale and MeP-K.

3.1 Current Capabilities- temperature scale realisation

3.1.1 Current realisation of the ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C

From 7 participants of the survey, three (UL, DTU and DFM) does not have current capability to realise ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C. SMU realises the ITS-90 temperature scale to 1600°C, using a tungsten lamp up to 2200 °C. RISE realises ITS-90 temperature scale to 2200 °C, CMI up to 1800°C, TUBITAK up to 3500 K and JV up to 1084 °C. All of the above-mentioned results can be viewed in graphical form in Fig.2.

Figure 2: Realization of ITS-90 temperature scale for temperature higher than 962 °C by the institutes

Do you currently realise ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C?

8 odpovedí

Apart from SMU all four mentioned institutes use copper as the fixed point for realisation of scale. SMU, JV, DFM and TUBITAK can also use silver fixed points. SMU and TUBITAK also realises the gold fixed point.

3.1.2 Other fixed points, e.g. for lower temperatures

The participating institutes have available a number of other fixed points at lower temperature.

CMI, SMU, JV and TUBITAK have fixed points In, Sn, Zn and Al. SMU is at the time of the survey waiting for delivery of a Cu cell and TUBITAK has TPW. RISE had Au and Ag. UL, DFM and DTU do not have fixed points for lower temperature. The presented results are presented in a pie chart in Fig. 3.

Which fixed point(s) do you use?

6 odpovedí

Figure 3: Used fixed points

3.1.3 Realisation of MeP-K for temperatures higher than 962 °C

Only TÜBITAK realises MeP-K currently in the temperature range 1000 K to 3500 K. This agrees with the project's main objective, which is to aid CMI, JV, RISE, DTU, SMU and UL in their efforts to build this capacity. Results are present in Fig. 4.

Do you currently realise MeP-K for temperatures higher than 962 °C?

8 odpovedí

Figure 4: Realization of MeP-K for temperature scale for temperature higher than 962 °C by the institutes

TÜBITAK has already implemented the following FP and HTFPs: Cu (1084,6200 °C), Fe-C (1153 °C), Co-C (1324 °C), Ru-C (1954 °C), Re-C (2474 °C), WC-C (2749 °C) and Ti-C (2759 °C). To realise MeP-K, TÜBITAK uses Relative primary Radiometry.

3.2 Current capabilities- available equipment

The second part of the survey was focused on available equipment in participating laboratories, manufacturing and modelling capabilities.

MultiFixRad

Overview of existing capabilities in less experienced institutes, Task 1.2, A1.2.1, A1.2.2

3.2.1 Interpolation device(s) for temperatures

SMU uses a photoelectric pyrometer FEP1C (SMU prototype), the working wavelength is 650 nm, focal length is 250 mm, and the diameter of the measurement spot is 1 mm.

JV uses Heitronics TRT.IV, working wavelength is 8-14 μm , working distance is 380 mm, and the diameter of the measurement spot is 5 mm.

RISE and CMI uses KE LP5, working wavelength is 650 nm, fixed focus at 800 mm, diameter of the measurement spot 1 mm.

TUBITAK uses InGaAs-based RT, TSP-2 (650 nm and 900 nm,) and KE LP5 (650 nm).

UL uses Heitronics, KT 19 II, working wavelength is 2 – 2,7 μm , working distance is 733 mm, diameter of the measurement spot is 12,7 mm.

DTU uses FTIR/grating spectrometer and cameras 400 nm to 20000 μm , 200-1000 mm working distance with spot size several mm.

DFM have available a homebuilt camera and silicon photodiode based pyrometer, working wavelength is 800 nm and 600 mm working distance. Measurement spot of around 1 mm diameter. Additionally Impac and other pyrometers for secondary use are available.

3.2.2 Availability to realise relative spectral characterisation of your interpolation device in house
SMU, TUBITAK and DTU can realise relative spectral characterisation of their own interpolation device directly in the lab. JV, RISE, DFM and CMI can realise relative spectral characterisation of their own interpolation device via another department in their institute. UL cannot realise relative spectral characterisation of own interpolation device. The percentage of laboratories which can realize the relative spectral characterisation of interpolation device can be seen in Fig.5.

Do you have availability to realise relative spectral characterisation of your interpolation device?

 Kopirovat

8 odpovedí

Figure 5: The availability to realization relative spectral characterisation of own interpolation device

3.2.3 Availability to realise SSE characterisation of your interpolation device

Only CMI cannot realise SSE characterisation of their own interpolation device, but KE LP5 was characterised in 2023 on the equipment borrowed from LNE-CNAM. Everyone else can characterise the SSE of their own interpolation device directly in the lab. The availability of SSE characterisation is presented in graphical form in Fig.6.

Do you have availability to realise SSE characterisation of your interpolation device?

8 odpovedí

Figure 6: The availability to realization SSE characterisation of own interpolation device

3.2.4 Availability to realise linearity characterisation of your interpolation device

RISE, TÜBITAK, DFM and DTU can characterise the linearity of their own interpolation device directly in lab. The number of laboratories that can realise linearity characterisation of their interpolation device can be seen in Fig.7.

Do you have availability to realise linearity characterisation of your interpolation device?

8 odpovedí

Figure 7: The availability to realization linearity characterisation of own interpolation device

3.2.5 Facility for filling HTFPs cells

RISE, TUBITAK, UL and CMI have available facilities for filling HTFPs cells. The other institutes do not. The results on filling capabilities of high temperature fixed point cells can be found in Fig. 8.

Do you have available facility for filling HTFPs cells?

8 odpovedí

Figure 8: The availability of facility for filling HTFPs cells

SMU has only (vertical) high temperature furnace (up to 1800 °C). RISE and UL have facilities for filling HTFPs cells in temperature up to 1500 °C. TÜBITAK possess a facility for filling in the temperature range 150 °C to 3000 °C. CMI has available a facility for filling in temperature up to 2500 °C.

3.2.6 Inhouse machining service

SMU, DFM and UL do not have access to machining service at their own institute. The other institutes do.

All five institutes (JV, RISE, TUBITAK, CMI, DTU) have mechanical workshop (JV, RISE and CMI without the possibility of modifying carbon components) and TÜBITAK has a CNC machine. The survey result is presented in Fig.9.

Do you have available machining service available in your institute?

8 odpovedí

Figure 9: The availability of machining service on own institute

3.2.7 Thermal modelling capabilities

SMU, RISE, DFM and UL do not have capabilities for thermal modelling. The other institutes do. The survey result is presented in Fig.10.

Do you have capabilities for thermal modelling?

8 odpovedí

Figure 10: The capability of thermal modelling

JV uses Comsol. TÜBITAK uses Comsol, Solid Works and Matlab. CMI uses Ansys Fluent. DTU realises simple modelling using basic heat transfer calculation in Excel.

3.2.8 Do you have capabilities for optics modelling?

In case of optics modelling, only JV, DFM and TÜBITAK have capabilities to realise it. JV realises basic ray tracing using Matlab. TÜBITAK and DFM uses Zemax. Optical modelling capabilities are presented in Fig.11.

Do you have capabilities for optics modelling?

8 odpovedí

Figure 11: The capability of optics modelling

3.2.9 Capabilities for radiometric modelling, e.g. emissivity?

JV uses Matlab and realises some analytical simplified models. RISE uses STEEP320. CMI uses free version of STEEP. TÜBITAK uses INCA33 (v 3.1) and STEEP3. DTU uses own simplified software in Excel for design of blackbody cavities. SMU, DFM and UL do not have capabilities for radiometric modelling. Radiometric modelling capabilities of involved institutes is presented in Fig.12.

Do you have capabilities for radiometric modelling, e.g. emissivity?

8 odpovedí

Figure 12: The capability of radiometric modelling

3.3 Future capabilities

The third part of the survey was devoted to the future plans and capabilities.

3.3.1 Do you plan to extend realisation of ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C?

JV and TÜBITAK do not plan to extend realisation of ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C. The other institutes do. The plans of extending the current ITS-90 temperature range beyond 962 °C of involved institutes is presented in Fig.13. and by which fixed point is presented in subsequent Fig.14.

Do you plan to extend realisation of ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C?

8 odpovedí

Figure 13: The extension of ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures higher than 962 °C

3.3.2 If yes, in which temperature range?

RISE plans to extend realisation of ITS-90 temperature scale for temperatures to 2600°C. UL plans to extend realisation of ITS-90 to copper. CMI to 2500 °C, DFM to 1560 °C and DTU to 1324 °C. SMU did not answer the question.

MultiFixRad

Overview of existing capabilities in less experienced institutes, Task 1.2, A1.2.1, A1.2.2

3.3.3 Which fixed point(s) do you plan to use?

SMU, RISE, UL, CMI, DTU and DFM plan to use copper. In addition this RISE, DFM and DTU plan to use silver. TÜBITAK plan to use only copper in the future.

Which fixed point(s) do you plan to use?

7 odpovedí

Figure 14: Planned fixed points to use

3.3.4 Do you plan to realise MeP-K for temperatures higher than 962 °C?

All institutes plan to realise MeP-K for temperatures higher than 962 °C. SMU and UL plan to realise MeP-K up to 1492 °C. JV in temperature range 1000 °C to 1800 °C. RISE plans to realise MeP-K up to 2600 °C, CMI up to 2500 °C, DFM up to 1560 °C and DTU up to 1324 °C. The proportion of what temperature ranges the involved institutes want to cover can be seen in Fig.15.

If yes, in which temperature range?

8 odpovedí

Figure 15: Temperature range of MeP-K, which you laboratories plan to realise MeP-K in future

MultiFixRad

Overview of existing capabilities in less experienced institutes, Task 1.2, A1.2.1, A1.2.2

3.3.5 Planed fixed point(s) to use

Laboratories plans to use following fixed points in a future for realisation of the MeP-K is listed in the following table:

institute	Al	Ag	Cu	Fe-C	Co-C	Pd-C	Re-C	Pt-C
SMU			X		X	X		
JV	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
RISE		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
TUBITAK						X	X	X
UL			X	X	X	X		
CMI			X		X	X	X	
DTU					X			
DFM		X	X			X		

3.3.6 Method for MeP-K realisation

JV, RISE plans to use 3 and more fixed points with interpolation. CMI and SMU plan to use method via relative radiometry via extrapolation from any fixed point and interpolation between multiple fixed points. DFM plans to use interpolation between fixed points and extrapolation. DTU plans to use relative radiometry via extrapolation from (any) fixed point and interpolation between multiple fixed points.

3.3.7 Any other information to share with the partners?

JV: "We will build software based on Matlab to analyse data in-use. We will build a pyrometer using commercial components."